

THE KOVUL PLANT

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Annotation: The main purpose of writing this article is to find out about the kovul plant, which belongs to the cauliflower family and is of interest to everyone, and how it spreads, how it grows and is widely used in medicine. I am applying to students.

Keywords: Kovul, medicinal plant, widely used in medicine, root bark, medicinal.

Kovul, kovar is a semi-shrub belonging to the family kovul. Stems and branches flat, leaves ovate, flowers large, white or pale pink. The fruit is red fleshy, with many seeds. Widespread in the rocky areas of the Crimea, the Caucasus, Central Asia, North Africa and the Mediterranean. It is grown in southern Europe. Kovul buds and fruits are eaten with vinegar or salt. The fruit contains 18% protein and 36% fat. It is a multi-seeded berry that grows in deserts and hills, along roadsides, on walls, and among crops. Its fruits are fleshy and up to 2 cm long. The seeds ripen in July-August. The fruits of this medicinal plant contain saponins, alkaloids, 32.9% carbohydrates, 150 mg of ascorbic acid, 3.75% fat, and the alkaloid stachidrin in the bark of the root. including Uzbekistan, Pakistan and India. The plant is cultivated in France, Spain, Italy, Algeria and Cyprus, Greece and North America and is a landscape decoration. The plant is named after the Dashti-Kavir desert in Iran. This is because squash is one of the most common plants in these areas.

Kovul is not only a medicinal plant but also used in food. The buds, buds, and growing fruits of the cauliflower are marinated in acetic acid and used in food as a medicine known as capers. The Hindus call the kovul cobra, kabra or kabarra, and they like to eat foods made with plant organs. In medicine, ripe fruits, leaves, twigs and root bark are used. In May-August, unopened buds and leaves are harvested. At the same time, the bark of young, woody twigs and roots is cut off, crushed and dried in the sun or at a temperature of 50-60 ° C. A tincture made from the bark has an appetizing effect. In folk medicine it is used to treat

purulent wounds. The newly peeled bark has a positive effect when applied to a sore tooth. It sometimes has an antiseptic effect on open purulent wounds. The plant is also used in the treatment of angina, thyrotoxicosis, hemorrhoids, diabetes. I would like to briefly tell you about the role of the Kovul medicinal plant in folk medicine. rod and root bark are applied. The bark is used to treat headaches, and the bark is used to treat blackheads. Ointment made from the roots and leaves is used to repair scabs and other wounds, fruit decoction strengthens the gums, relieves toothache, and root decoction cures jaundice. and infused for 10 minutes and taken 2 tablespoons 3 times a day, followed by an alcoholic infusion of kavul root. Due to the high content of rutin in kovul, it is used to lower blood pressure.

Kovul is a useful drug for women, and its consumption protects the body from oncological diseases. If you eat a few cups before a meal during an anorexic summer, it will whet your appetite To make a tincture from the root bark, pour 0.5 liters of boiling water on 20 g of peeled bark and let it rest for 1-2 hours. Drink 1/2 cup three times daily before meals.

In skin diseases Take 2 teaspoons of dried rind, pour a glass of water and simmer on low heat for 10-15 minutes. Affected skin is often wiped with a chilled decoction.

Thyrotoxicosis, hemorrhoids Take 1 teaspoon of dried fruit, add 200 ml of water and boil for 3-4 minutes. Chilled decoction is taken 1–2 tablespoons three times daily before meals.

In diabetes mellitus Take 1 tablespoon of dried twigs and leaves, add 200 ml of water and boil for 4-5 minutes. Chilled decoction is drunk 2 tablespoons 3–4 times a day.

Kovul is a blue-stemmed plant that grows to a height of 2-2.5 m. The short-flowered flower is located in the busy armpit. its name is not yet known to science, but some scholars have suggested that its original homeland was Greece. The roots of the Kovul plant dissolve various barriers and release acid, which allows them to grow freely even on paved bituminous land. As long as it is selected, it is a type of plant rich in sap. Blooms from May to November, honey, aphids, stems thorny, branched, hairless or sparsely hairy. Flowers are white before the flowering season. It also contains protein, fats, carbohydrates, essential oils, K, Mg, Na, Ca, P, F, Zn, Cu, Mn. It is a multi-seeded berry that grows in deserts and hills, along roadsides, on walls, among crops, and its fruits are fleshy, up to 2 cm long. The fruits of this medicinal plant contain saponins,

alkaloids, 32.9% carbohydrates, 150 mg of ascorbic acid, 3.75% oil, and the alkaloid stachidrin in the root bark.

The kovul plant can be harvested in 3 years, 1600 seedlings per hectare can be planted. The most important thing is that the pumpkin buds all summer long. Collected only on capture in 8–10 days. Therefore, it is sold at high prices in world markets. A well-developed plant can yield up to 3 kg per harvest. At the end of the season, this figure is 7.5 kg, 12 tons per hectare. Given that it starts at \$ 18,000, then the total annual revenue averages \$ 18,000. This figure is growing from year to year. This thorny shrub that grows on the ground does not choose a place, it is resistant to drought and cold. It grows from May to October. It blooms in pieces. Then a berry with a cell flesh bears fruit. This two-tiered fruit looks like a watermelon. Only dwarf watermelons ... It grows naturally in the mountainous areas of the country. In particular, it can be found in Zaamin, Jalal-Abad, Forish, Sharof Rashidov of Jizzakh region, Bulakbashi of Andijan region, Chust and Kosonsoy districts of Namangan region, in the foothills of Tashkent region. To date, 12 exporters in the Jizzakh region are engaged in the export of kavul.

It is no secret that squash, which was once neglected and grows in the hills and deserts, is now a medicinal plant from root to leaf and in high demand. More precisely, until recent years we were unaware of such a treasure. Today it is widely used in pharmaceuticals, food industry and folk medicine.

References:

1. O'zME. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000 ;
2. from the national encyclopedia collection ;
3. Rakhmatov Utkir, editor-in-chief of “Khalk Sozi” and “ Narodnoye Slava” newspapers;
4. Internet and websites.
5. Nodira ARABOVA, Candidate of Biological Sciences. Magazine "Health".